

Exploring Syllable Structure in Jhangvi: A CV Phonology Analysis

Dr. Muhammad Asad Habib

Associate Professor, Department of English Language & Literature, University of Lahore, Lahore.

Dr. Muhammad Asif

Assistant Professor, Department of English and Literary Studies, University of Management and Technology, Lahore.

Dr. Shafaq Fayyaz

Assistant Professor, Department of English Language & Literature, University of Lahore, Lahore.

Muhammad Imran Afzal

Ph.D. Scholar (Corresponding Author), University of Lahore, Lahore.

Liaqat Ali Mohsin

Ph.D. Scholar, University of Lahore, Lahore.

ABSTRACT: This study aims to establish a theoretical understanding of the syllable structure of the Jhangvi language. The analysis employs the CV phonology theory to investigate the composition of syllables. Thirty-four native speakers of the Jhangvi dialect were chosen for data collection, utilizing interviews and focus group discussions as primary tools. The participants, all residents of the Jhang district, are native speakers of Jhangvi and provided essential insights. Purposive sampling was employed to ensure data relevance. The findings indicate that Jhangvi speakers utilize seven primary patterns for syllable construction: V, VV, CV, CVC, VC, CVV, and CVVC. Notably, these patterns exhibit a closer resemblance to Punjabi rather than the Saraiki dialect. The findings underscore the necessity for further linguistic exploration of the Jhangvi language, illuminating its unique characteristics and linguistic dynamics.

Keywords: Generative Phonology, CV Phonology, Three-Tiered Model, Jhangvi Dialect

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1. Introduction

The Jhangvi dialect lacks research on its linguistic features. Moreover, it is not taught and studied in local educational institutions. It also lacks prestige as compared to English and Urdu Language. The speakers of the Jhangvi dialect are turning their attention towards other more prestigious varieties. It is not a well-documented language and its written convention is similar to that of the Punjabi language which is Shahmukhi. But there are certain features of Jhangvi which are difficult to express in Shahmukhi's script. Another important issue with Jhangvi in particular and other indigenous varieties, in general, is the issue of prestige. Jhangvi like other varieties of Punjabi lacks prestige. English and Urdu as compared to Jhangvi enjoy prestige. The Jhangvi dialect holds a prominent position in the

linguistic landscape, spanning the region from Khanewal to the Jhang district. Predominantly spoken in District Jhang, it owes its nomenclature to this geographical locale. Positioned as an intermediary between Punjabi and Saraiki, it is identified by multiple names, including Chenavari, Jhangvi, Changvi, and Niswani.

English is the official language of Pakistan and enjoys the status of the language of trade, court and other major offices. At the same time, Urdu is the national language of Pakistan (Rehman, 2019). This puts Jhangvi speakers under immense pressure to use English and Urdu in their Formal Communication. Because of the widespread criticism of indigenous and regional languages in Pakistan, the transmission of Jhangvi to the next generation has slowed considerably in recent years (Abbasi, 2010). Jhangvi can only be spoken in its native rural areas. The regional languages of Punjabi and Lahndi are encroaching on Jhangvi's territory. Even more significantly, Urdu and English are exerting tremendous pressure on the vast bulk of indigenous tongues. Dialects that have only oral traditions and no written literature have little hope of preserving their language's vocabulary. One language (either Urdu or English) eventually replaces another. Now more than ever, it is critical to record every 'endangered dialect. This elevates their status as spoken tongues.

This study presents a theoretical examination of the syllabic structure within the Jhangvi language. As asserted by Kenstowicz (1994), the concept of a syllable serves as a fundamental element for comprehending the phonological framework of any given language. Syllables are the building blocks of words, and there is a unique pattern to how each language puts them together. All languages have their own set of guidelines for how these words can be combined. Despite numerous attempts by scholars to provide various definitions of syllables, a comprehensive definition remains elusive (Trask 2013). Roach (2009) proposes that the syllable can be defined both phonologically and phonetically. From a phonetic standpoint, it is characterized by the articulatory manner of speech sounds, consisting of a nucleus that is unobstructed and louder compared to the surrounding marginal sounds at the onset and coda of the syllable. Meanwhile, phonologically, it can be discerned by examining the phonotactics specific to a particular language.

Referred to as Jhangvi, Jhangochi, or Rachnavi, this dialect is an integral part of the Punjabi language spoken in Pakistani Punjab. Rooted in tradition, Jhangvi is the oldest among its counterparts and is synonymous with the city of Jhang. Sahiwal also recognizes it by the name Jhangvi, while Chenavri and Changvi are alternative appellations (Grierson, 1928).

Geographically, Jhangvi extends from Khanewal to Jhang, straddling the opposite banks of the Ravi and Chenab rivers, and reaching as far as the Gujranwala district. It continues its linguistic journey through Bahawalnagar and Chishtian along the Sutlej river. Noteworthy characteristics distinguish the Jhangochi dialect from other Punjabi varieties in the region. The Jhang district, a cradle of rich cultural heritage, claims literary significance, being associated with the creation of renowned epic romances like Heer Ranjha and Mirza Sahiba. This linguistic variant thrives in the Bar areas of Punjab, such as Sandal Bar, Kirana Bar, Neeli Bar, Ganji Bar, and extends from Khanewal to Jhang. It also encompasses Chiniot, Faisalabad, Chakwal, Mandi Bahauddin, and Hafizabad (Fatima, 2022).

The Jangal Bar tract in Faisalabad District, Okara, Pakpattan, and territories once part of the Montgomery District, contribute to the diverse linguistic tapestry of this region. The Sandal Bar, situated between the Chenab and Ravi rivers in the Rechna Doab region, earned its name from "Bar," signifying a wooded area unfit for agriculture due to the lack of resources, specifically water. This expanse, attributed to Dulla Bhatti's grandfather Saandal, was historically part of the Jhang District but now spans Faisalabad, Jhang, and Toba Tek Singh districts.

1.1 Classification

Jhangvi is classified as part of the group of languages called Lahnda. Lahnda is the name given to the group of languages spoken in western Punjab. The word Lahnda in Punjabi means the west or the direction where the sun sets (Grierson, 1928). It belongs to the north-western Lahnda which is the subgroup of Indo-Aryan Language (Glottolog 4.8).

Middle-Modern Indo-Aryan (209)

- ▼ Continental Indo-Aryan (168)
 - ► Indo-Aryan Eastern zone (29)
 - ▼ Indo-Aryan Northwestern zone (19)
 - **Paisaci Prakrit**
 - ▼ Sindhi-Lahnda (18)
 - ▼ Greater Panjabic (9)
 - ► Eastern Panjabic (2)
 - ▼ Hindko-Siraiki (4)
 - ► Hindko (2)
 - ▼ Siraikic (2)
 - **Inku**
 - ▼ **Saraiki**
 - ► Central Siraiki
 - Jhangvi

According to Glottolog 4.8, the Jhangvi dialect belongs to Central Saraiki belt which is the part of Sindhi-Lahnda.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The Jhangvi dialect is indigenous variety of Punjabi language and due to the lack of work on Linguistic aspect of Jhangvi a dire need is identified to work on this dialect. This work is aspired to add prestige to Jhangvi by making it an object of research. Thus, the researcher endeavors to give a detailed phonological description of the Jhangvi syllable in the light of CV phonology.

1.3 Objective of the Study

The objective of the study is to identify, describe and explain the syllable structure of the Jhangvi language in the light of Generative grammar.

2. Theoretical Framework

The study employs the CV Phonology theory as a theoretical framework to investigate the syllable structure of the Jhangvi Dialect. It is a generative theory introduced by George N. Clements and Samuel Jay Keyser in 1983, CV Phonology theory offers a valuable framework for analyzing syllables. This theory serves three main functions: firstly, it provides universal rules governing syllable structure; secondly, it elucidates the variations in syllable structure across languages (syllable typology); and finally, it furnishes rules that govern the specific syllable structure of a given language (Clements & Keyser, 1983). CV phonology propagates a three-tiered construction of a syllable: a syllable, a CV and segmental tier. These layers are presented by the word /bɪn/ in the figure below.

Figure 1: Syllable tiers

The figure 1 explains the three-tiered model where segmental tier is dominated by the CV tier. Segmental tier is the bundles of distinctive feature for any given segment of sound. Hence it explains the differentiating values of different phonemes. CV tier differentiates the Peaks and non-peaks. In figure 1, V element is showing the peak of the syllable while C elements are showing the non-peaks of the syllables. According to it, only peak elements due to high sonority can make syllable while non-peak elements are optional and thus termed as marginal elements. This is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2 Syllable tiers mentioning sonority

As mentioned in figure 2 phoneme /a/ is making the peak of the syllable due to high sonority [+sonorous] value than the marginal elements thus it will be [+syll] while /k/ and /r/ are low in sonority [-sonorous] and cannot make peak accordingly they are [-syll]. Clement and Keyser (1983) positions different phonemes according to the varying sonority.

3. Methods

3.1 Population and Sample

The population of the research is the native speakers of the Jhangvi language in Jhang District. A sample of 40 Jhangvi speakers belonging to the same social and regional backgrounds are selected from the population. For the selection of the sample, the purposive sampling technique is followed. The sample consists of males and females, though gender is not a variable of the present study yet it is collected from both in natural settings as language is used by them. These talks are recorded to maintain the record of the proceedings. The following points are kept in mind to select the sample. Participants must be:

- Native speakers of Jhang
- Born and brought up in Jhang district and are not migrants
- People from different positions in the town
- Free from hearing or speaking disorders

3.2 Instruments

This study employs a qualitative approach, utilizing Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) and semi-structured interviews as its primary instruments. Three focus groups were formed, each comprising six to seven members fluent in Jhangvi, the native language. Participants were purposefully selected from diverse backgrounds to ensure comprehensive data collection. Attendees primarily included high school teachers, supplemented by representatives from local administration, law enforcement, college students, and various professional development and training centres.

These 20 speakers are divided into three groups on the basis of age, gender, regional background, and proximity:

- In group 1, the researcher is taking 3 males and 3 females ranging from age 15 to 30 years.
- In group 2, the researcher has taken 4 males and 3 females ranging from age 30 to 50 years.
- In group 3, the researcher has taken 4 males and 3 females ranging from age 50 & to above years.

Along with focus group discussions, semi-structured interviews were conducted to gather data. Twenty native speakers are selected for interviews. These interviews maintained an open format, allowing for flexible discussion on various topics relevant to the study. Derived from societal contexts, the interview topics spanned areas such as development, innovation, employment, business transactions, legal proceedings and political issues.

4. Data Analysis

4.1 Punjabi Syllable Structure

This section offers a detailed description of the Jhangvi syllable structure, which bears similarities to Punjabi and other Indo-Aryan languages (Habib & Khan, 2021). Jhangvi exhibits seven distinct syllable structures: V, VV, CV, VC, CVC, CVV and CVCC. These structures are elucidated through the lens of CV Phonology theory, wherein syllables are analyzed in terms of their constituent consonant (C) and vowel (V) elements, with CC representing consonant clusters and VV representing complex vowel peaks.

Herein, various types of syllables encountered in the Jhangvi language will be illustrated, alongside their phonotactic constraints. This explanation will delineate the methods by which C and V elements are combined within syllables, guided by constraints on syllabic configuration acting as filtering mechanisms, permitting only specific CV sequences. A comprehensive inventory of potential syllables in Punjabi is presented in the accompanying table, supplemented with illustrative examples.

As propounded by Clements and Keyser (1983), the syllable serves a pivotal role in all languages by defining the syllabicity of segments, thereby regulating the combinations of C and V elements within words. In essence, it controls the features that constitute CV structures. Notably, the Jhangvi dialect manifests its own unique amalgamation of C and V combinations, which will be delineated in subsequent sections.

After the collection of data, data was analyzed and seven patterns were found in Jhangvi dialects. As mentioned above CV phonology theory was employed to analyze and present data. These seven patterns are shown in the table.

Table 1 Syllable Patterns in Jhangvi Language

Syllable templates	Lexeme	Gloss
V	e:	This
VV	aɪ	Came (plural)
CV	b ^h a:	Price
VC	əɟ	Fire
CVC	p ^h ək	Fodder
CVV	dʒei	Oat
CVCC	kənd	Wall

The detail of each pattern is discussed in detail in the next sections

4.2 V Syllable Template

Jhangvi exhibits a V syllable template that consists of a short vowel as in /e/, and a long vowel as in /a:/. For this study, short and long vowels are considered as /V/ and considered as simple rhymes. This syllable type omits both the onset consonant and the coda consonants, making them syllables with a structure of [-C+V], wherein certain elements are on the periphery. The vowel element serves as the nucleus of the syllable due to its sonority, while the consonant elements are considered peripheral as they lack sonority (Clements & Keyser, 1983). Thus, Jhangvi possesses all three types in their syllable structure. Examples of Simple rhyme and complex rhyme are mentioned in figure 3 and 4.

Figure 3 Simple Rhyme in Jhangvi

4.3 VV Syllable Template

The Jhangvi dialect also possesses complex rhymes with VV configuration. This configuration is mostly found in the open syllables as in /aɪ/ 'came' used for plural marking with (-C + VV) showing the absence of the initial and final element. An example of this configuration is given in figure 4.

Figure 4 Complex Rhyme (VV) in the Jhangvi Dialect

4.4 CV Syllable Template

The third syllable template found in the Jhangvi Dialect is CV. This template is used most by the Jhangvi speakers and it is found in the majority of the collected data. As mentioned by Clements & Keyser (1983) CV is the canonical syllable template in all the languages and Jhangvi complies with this in this regard. It comprises the presence of the initial element (+C) along with simple rhyme as in figure 5 and also with complex rhyme as mentioned in figure 7. An example of this configuration is mentioned in figure 5.

Figure 5 Initial element (C) with simple rhyme (V) in the Jhangvi Dialect

4.5 VC Syllable Template

The fourth syllable template present in the Jhangvi dialect is the VC configuration. This configuration allows the tail element along with simple Rhyme at peak position, thus making a (-C +V +C) template. Both short and long vowels can be seen in this template as in the word /əkh / 'eye and in /a:ljə/ 'nest'. The example of this template is explained in figure 6.

Figure 6 Final Consonant Element (C) with simple rhyme (V) in the Jhangvi Dialect

4.6 CVC Syllable Template

The Jhangvi dialect also exhibits CVC configuration in syllables. This template shows the presence of both marginal elements along with the syllable peak thus making the syllable (+C -V +C). An example of this type of syllable template can be found in words like / bhuk/ and / phut/. This is shown in the figure 7.

Figure 7 Marginal elements (C) with simple rhyme (V) in the Jhangvi Dialect

4.7 CVV Syllable Template

The Jhangvi dialect possesses CVV syllable configuration, unlike the Punjabi Language that does not possess a complex rhyme or diphthong in the peak position (Habib & Khan, 2021). Jhangvi on the other hand possesses complex rhyme. The existence of this configuration is found in no tail element environment only in the data. In closed syllable configuration, complex rhymes (VV) are found absent as in the word like /t̪aɪ/ 'aunt' with (+C+VV) configuration. It is shown in figure 8.

Figure 8 Marginal element (C) with Complex Rhyme (V) in the Jhangvi Dialect

4.8 CVCC Syllable Template

The last template in the Jhangvi dialect is the CVCC template. This configuration allows consonant clusters at the tail or coda position. The consonant cluster at the initial or tail position is not very common in Punjabi or Urdu language but is present in the Jhangvi dialect. An example of this type of configuration can be seen in the word /pund/ 'heap of cloths' that makes a (+C+V+C+C) configuration. An example of this template is shown in figure 9.

Figure 9 Marginal element (C) with Complex Rhyme (V) in the Jhangvi Dialect

5. Discussion and Conclusion

This study is a qualitative analysis of the syllable structure of the Jhangvi Dialect. The data selected for this study is taken purposefully from 40 native speakers of Jhangvi residing in Jhang District. Focus group discussions and semi-structured interviews are used as tools for the data collection. CV phonology theory is taken as a theoretical framework for this study. The data revealed that the Jhangvi dialect uses seven different syllable templates. These templates are shown in C and V notation in accordance with the CV phonology conventions. These templates are V, VV, CV, VC, CVC, CVV and CVCC. The results of the study show similarities with the Punjabi and Urdu languages which are spoken in the area with greater prestige in terms of social acceptance. V, VV, CV, VC, CVC, and CVV are common in the Punjabi language (Habib & Khan) while CVCC is common in the Saraiki dialect (Atta et al., 2022).

As indicated earlier, there is a significant lack of linguistic research on the Jhangvi language, which emphasizes the need for comprehensive studies in this area. While this paper primarily explores the syllable structure of Jhangvi, future research should broaden its focus to include other dimensions of Jhangvi phonology. Although the current study employs a CV phonology framework, additional theoretical approaches should be considered to enhance our understanding of the language. Furthermore, the limited research in Dialectology also points to a pressing need for more work in this field. It is recommended that Jhangvi be incorporated into academic syllabi, which would not only help preserve the language but also empower Jhangvi-speaking communities.

6. References

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